

PETER HAAS AWARD DINNER SPEECH

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I would like to thank the 11th IEEE International Pulsed Power Conference for selecting me to receive the Peter Haas Pulsed Power Award. I have worked with many outstanding people in the pulsed power community and they have all contributed to my winning this award. It is indeed an honor to be included with the previous recipients of this award: Kris Kristiansen, Art Guenther, Gerry Yonas, Alan Kolb and Bernie Berstein. Tonight I would like to share some of my experiences.

My academic training was in nuclear physics, which is not the recommended curriculum for a career in pulsed power research and development. In fact, I do not recall ever hearing the term pulsed power while I was in school. My first step toward pulsed power, although I did not realize it at the time, was receiving a Commission in the United State Air Force. Upon completion of my Ph.D. work at the Ohio State University in 1969, I tried to get assigned to the nuclear structure laboratory at Wright-Patterson AFB, Ohio. Instead the Air Force assigned me to the Air Force Weapons Laboratory at Kirtland AFB, New Mexico. This unplanned action changed the whole course of my life and filled it with exiting technical activities far beyond my academic dreams.

The information that I received from the Air Force Weapons Laboratory stated that it was the Air Force center for nuclear research. I interviewed with all the Laboratory's divisions, but found none that were doing work that as a nuclear physicist I would consider nuclear research. I did, however, find a lot of work on nuclear weapons effects. I chose to work in the Technology Division, which seemed to be doing most of the fundamental research and development. Art Guenther was the Chief Scientist of the division at this time. My particular branch was focused on developing and evaluating techniques to produce intense bursts of x-rays and neutrons to simulate the prompt radiation from a nuclear weapon. I rapidly learned that pulsed power was a critical enabling technology for all approaches and that it was often the limiting factor.

My first assignment at the Air Force Weapons Laboratory was working with John Nuckolls and Lowell Woods at the Lawrence Livermore Laboratory on development of a fusion radiation source called the micro-bomb. It involved the use of a very high magnetic field, intense high energy electron beam and a high power laser. My role centered on design of the intense electron beam portion of the project. The desired technology elements existed at our two laboratories, but their required performance and integration to demonstrate the micro-bomb feasibility proved to be well beyond the state-of-the-art. The project was abandoned, but it had introduced me to many ideas that would be important in subsequent work.

The most popular pulsed radiation source in the early 1970's was the dense plasma focus. Joe Mather and Ken Ware at Los Alamos Laboratory were the US leaders and Dick Gullickson at

the Air Force Weapons Laboratory had built a small device to study radiation optimization techniques. Our Laboratory had also contracted with Physics International to build a large 500kJ device. We pursued many efforts to optimize the radiation output, including the use of shaped electrodes, various gas fills, laser blow-off of high atomic number material for x-ray enhancement and use of a deuterium-tritium gas mixture for neutron enhancement. None of these techniques led to the required large increase in radiation output. The dense plasma focus did provide the best radiation source for piece part testing for many years and continues to attract research interest.

Another approach was to use lasers or electron beams to heat plasmas. We investigated both, but favored electron beams because of their overall energy efficiency advantage. My branch purchased a 3 MeV FX 25 Van de Graaff pulsed electron beam machine to begin in-house research. Since I had spent 4 years in graduate school working with a high voltage Van de Graaff, I led the initial work on this machine, which looked almost like a toy compared to those of my nuclear physics world. Later we scaled work to the 5-10 MeV range using the FX-100 and PR 1590 machines that had been purchased for gamma ray effects testing. We were not able to produce substantial x-rays, but did acquire knowledge used later charged particle beam weapon research.

It was in early 1971 that Peter Turchi and I accidentally ended up sharing an office and spent a lot of time in search of a new approach to produce the required intense burst of x-rays. These investigations culminated with the invention of the hollow plasma electromagnetic implosion radiation source, which was subsequently developed under the SHIVA program at the Air Force Weapons Laboratory and under different names at other organizations. We coined the term electromagnetic implosion to distinguish it from the fusion z-pinch work that relied on resistive heating of the imploded plasma, whereas our concept delivered most of the energy during the implosion phase. By avoiding the use of the term z-pinch, which many people at the time thought would not work, we obtained funds to demonstrate the feasibility of the hollow plasma implosion radiation source. The hollow plasma liner could be produced by initial ionization of a cylindrical foil, array of many thin wires or hollow gas puff. We chose to begin with thin foils since they were most compatible with pulsed power technology that we could afford.

We needed a capacitor bank that had a faster current rise time and higher voltage than those developed for dense plasma focus work. We wanted to operate in air to reduce costs, but were told my many that it could not be done. It was then that Peter and I met Jon Farber, who worked in another division at the Air Force Weapons Laboratory, and learned that he had built a bank called CREST for flyer plate shock simulation. Its design parameters were 0.5 microsecond rise time, 50kV charge voltage and 500kJ stored energy. It lived in a bunker near the runway. It sounded great so we began preparations for plasma implosion experiments. One of our diagnosticians was so enthusiastic that he wanted to close down the east-west runway so that he could have longer diagnostic tubes. Jon believed that the secret to operating in air at high voltage was brown paper and high humidity, so the bank operated in a man made cloud. The bank used solid dielectric switches and it was difficult to tell by sound whether it was firing properly or blowing up. Above 42.5kV it turned out to always be the latter. Grounding was a problem and the bank controls were operated using a wooden ruler with the metal edge removed, since arcing

occurred even in the control van as the ground floated up in voltage. We never achieved the required performance parameters, but one implosion picture generated enough interest to support development of a dedicated capacitor bank for implosion experiments.

The parameters for this bank were, not surprisingly, to be 0.5 microsecond rise time, 50kV, and 500kJ. Solid dielectric switches remained the only low inductance switch option. We were allocated a small amount of space in the new pulsed power building. Every couple of weeks Peter and I would secretly move our dividing wall to enlarge our work space. Several years later, of course, the project occupied the entire building. To avoid the break down problems encountered at CREST, we enclosed the entire bank in one atmosphere of sulfur hexafluoride gas. Part of the time the bank performed up to our expectations, but switch pre-fires and hang-fires, which even with the help of the Charlie Martin and others we were never able to overcome, severely limited our research. It was also during this period that we lost Jon Farber as a team member. He left soon after being frightened by the failure of the nearby carbon dioxide laser bank while he was installing a heavy switch plate on the SHIVA bank. He dropped the plate on his foot and then jumped and hit his head on the transmission plate. Two weeks later he worked for the Defense Nuclear Agency. Despite our difficulties, through dedication and long hours, our team was able to make enough technical progress justify building a higher energy capacitor bank.

The need to get away from solid dielectric switches was clear if we were to have a productive research program. We needed to be able to concentrate on load performance and not capacitor bank performance. For performance, cost and statistical reliability we wanted to avoid having a switch for each capacitor as had been done in the Los Alamos Syllac bank and in dense plasma focus banks. We worked with Physics International to develop a pressurized low inductance rail gap switch. A mixture of Argon and sulfur hexafluoride gases gave the best performance and electrical performance was very good, but unfortunately mechanical performance was not satisfactory. A more robust variation of the rail gap switch was developed by Maxwell Laboratories and they subsequently won the contract to build the 1 megajoule SHIVA capacitor bank. The large transmission lines were made of aluminum siding with mylar insulation and king size water beds to hold them together with gravity. The bank worked perfectly, passing its acceptance test of 25 full energy shots in 24 hours without any failures. This development, which was a major advancement in pulsed power technology, was jointly sponsored by the Air Force Weapons Laboratory and the Defense Nuclear Agency, with Pete Haas a strong supporter.

To the amazement of many, the capacitor bank was no longer the limitation, but several more years were required before power flow problems in the intense radiation environment were overcome. Many electrode variations were explored to find a way to simultaneously have a low inductance transmission line, hold off high voltage and shield the vacuum insulator from the intense UV radiation. When we were able to successfully deliver the electrical power to the implosion load, the experimental results matched our theoretical predictions very well. This led of course to a desire for more energy. With Sandia National Laboratories we designed a water line system called Phoenix, but funding constraints prevented us from following this conventional route. Instead, we increased the energy of the bank to 9.5 megajoules using high energy density capacitors and renamed it SHIVA STAR. The conservatively designed original rail gap switches

were able to handle the increased stress, but with the additional capacitance the bank was too slow to drive fast plasma implosions. This limitation was overcome by using the bank to charge an inductive store and then using either fuse or plasma flow opening switches to rapidly switch the energy into the implosion load. Our work was technically successful, producing over a megajoule of x-rays in a pulse, but the Air Force lost interest in funding nuclear weapons effects research. Continuing work at Sandia National Laboratories and Los Alamos National Laboratory has advanced performance of plasma implosion loads to the level first predicted in 1971.

The potential for electromagnetically driving plasma implosions using explosive magnetic flux compression generators was attractive from the beginning. Work beginning in 1971 concentrated on very fast plate generators to directly drive implosions. The Air Force Weapons Laboratory and Los Alamos National Laboratory jointly pursued this work for many years, but it proved very technically challenging and difficult to diagnostic. A shift to inductive stores with fuse or plasma flow opening switches provided the opportunity to use high energy helical explosive generators. The work published by Alexander Pavlovskii further inspired the technology push in this direction. As the Air Force interest in radiation sources waned we became a secondary participant with Los Alamos National Laboratory, which continued to make progress in the use of large explosive generators to drive plasma implosions. We did export many good people to Los Alamos National Laboratory as a result of these interactions. Our present interest is on smaller explosive generators with power conditioning for driving high power microwave loads.

An early branch off from the nuclear radiation effects simulation business was the investigation of high current, high energy electron beams as possible charged particle beam weapons. This also included work on collective ion acceleration. We started by using existing machines built for gamma ray simulation - the FX 100 and PR 1590 at the Air Force Weapons Laboratory and the HERMES machine at Sandia National Laboratories. The plan was to condition the output beam to obtain the parameters required for stable propagation in open air. It turned out to be impossible to achieve stable propagation using these machines. The beams hosed in a wild fashion, sometimes turning almost 180 degrees. One of the most frightening accidents happened one night while we were firing the FX 100 into open air. An Air Force Captain, who was also the safety officer, was guarding the door to make sure that no one entered the test area when he realized that he had not pulled the film in the open shutter camera. Not thinking, he rushed in to correct the problem while the Van de Graaff was charging. The machine pre-fired sending out an intense electron beam. Hearing the sound the Captain threw himself to the concrete floor, thereby injuring his back. The electron beam, of course, was long gone by the time he heard the sound. Fortunately, the beam did not turn toward his location as it had done on previous shots and he did not receive a hazardous radiation dose.

It was apparent that we needed to build a specially designed machine to achieve the beam parameters necessary for stable propagation in open air. Over dinner one night Gerry Yonas and I agreed to commit Sandia National Laboratories and the Air Force Weapons Laboratory to jointly build the required accelerator and we were subsequently able to get the Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency to contribute substantial funding. A timely publication by Alexander Pavlovskii on the LIU-10 and PBFA technology provided the building blocks for RADLAC.

Ken Prestwich was the technical leader with support from Tom Martin in this challenging accelerator development. Stable open air propagation of the RADLAC electron beam was successfully achieved in a series of night time firings from a hill top on Kirtland AFB. Unfortunately, the range of the beam compared to the accelerator size was considered too little for most military missions and so the charged particle beam weapons applications program was abandoned until basic research substantially improved accelerator technology. However, technology developed in this effort was critical to early successes in the high power microwave area.

The pulsed power and beam dynamics work for charged particle beams provided a sound basis for rapid development of high power microwave devices, which did not have a propagation distance limitation. Almost immediately gigawatt power levels were achieved using virtual cathode oscillators on existing electron beam accelerators. This proved to be a very cost effective way to provide high power RF sources for laboratory effects tests, but was uninteresting for applications outside the laboratory. Therefore, a series of increasingly smaller and where possible more powerful machines were developed to power advanced high power microwave devices. Then came requirements for rep-rates up to several kilohertz, longer life times and higher reliability. High power microwaves have become the core focus of our pulsed power activities.

Interestingly as some of the Air Force Phillips Laboratory's requirements for pulsed power for high power microwaves have evolved, they are approaching the parameters required for many commercial applications. Hopefully with this synergism, affordable pulsed power solutions for both military and commercial applications can be achieved. I believe that further advances in size, weight and performance of pulsed power are required to reach this potential and open new avenues of research and development. At the same time there is an exciting next generation of large pulsed power machines about to be built. I believe that the future for pulsed power is bright and that it will cover a wide spectrum of applications.

Thank you for your attention and thanks again for the Peter Haas Pulsed Power Award.